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Smallest perceivable interaural time differences

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It is well-established that the smallest discrimination thresholds for interaural time differences (ITDs) are near $10\ \mu\text{s}$ for normal hearing listeners. However, little is known about the hearing and training status of the test subjects from past studies. Previous studies also did not explicitly focus on the identification of the optimal stimulus and measurement technique to obtain the smallest threshold ITDs. Therefore, the first goal of the current study was to identify the stimulus and experimental method that maximizes ITD sensitivity. The second goal was to provide a precise threshold ITD reference value for both well-trained and un-trained normal hearing listeners using the optimal stimulus and method. The stimulus that yielded the lowest threshold ITD was Gaussian noise, band-pass filtered from 20 to 1400 Hz, presented at 70 dB sound pressure level. The best method was a two-interval procedure with an interstimulus interval of 50 ms. The average threshold ITD for this condition at the 75% correct level was $6.9\ \mu\text{s}$ for nine trained listeners and $18.1\ \mu\text{s}$ for 52 un-trained listeners. © 2019 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.5087566>

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I. INTRODUCTION

Humans and many animals use their two ears to localize sounds within their surroundings. The differences in acoustic path lengths from a sound source to the two ears causes an interaural time difference (ITD), while an interaural level difference (ILD) is mainly caused by the head acoustically shadowing the contralateral ear. For humans, the cue that facilitates the most accurate sound localization (as small as 1° in azimuth) is the ITD (Mills, 1958).

To study ITD sensitivity in isolation, i.e., without ILDs, experiments using a pair of “at the ear” stimulators were conducted soon after the invention of a useable loudspeaker (Thompson, 1878). Early studies reported a remarkable precision of the binaural system, with threshold ITDs orders of magnitude smaller than temporal difference detection thresholds for all other sensory modalities (see, e.g., Klemm, 1920, who introduced a new “unit” to describe threshold ITDs, which we now call the microsecond). Precise and systematic studies have been conducted to determine threshold ITDs (Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956; Klumpp and Eady, 1956; Mills, 1958) and it has been consistently reported that the lowest ITD detection thresholds are very close to $10\ \mu\text{s}$.

The question remains whether an ITD of $10\ \mu\text{s}$ is the smallest ITD that an average trained normal hearing listener can discriminate for an optimal stimulus and paradigm. Neither the above-mentioned studies nor any follow-up study have explicitly attempted to answer this question. On the other hand, many studies, reviews, textbooks, and spatial sound engineers appear to require the smallest threshold ITD

as a reference or benchmark (e.g., Hudspeth, 1989; Moore, 2012). To date, Klumpp and Eady’s (1956) report of $9\ \mu\text{s}$ is commonly accepted as the best available benchmark, even though Klumpp and Eady did not explicitly say that they were attempting to find the optimal stimulus that yields the minimum thresholds.

In recent decades, methods have shifted from constant stimulus paradigms to staircase procedures, where the ITD is adaptively reduced after a given number of correct responses and increased after an incorrect response (Levitt, 1971). Furthermore, typical interval durations have decreased from 2 s (Klumpp and Eady, 1956) to 0.5 s or even shorter. Next, signal generation has changed from analogue to digital. While the type of signal generation and adaptive measurements are not expected to affect ITD sensitivity (e.g., Trahiotis *et al.*, 1990), interval durations and the interstimulus interval may potentially have an influence. It is also possible that some previously untested stimulus may provide even better ITD sensitivity than those tested by Klumpp and Eady (1956). One recent study (Brughera *et al.*, 2013) has revisited pure-tone threshold ITDs using the above-mentioned modern standard techniques. They reported that best sensitivity occurs between 700–1000 Hz, which is in line with the historic references but more precise. However, their reported thresholds are much higher. Only their two most sensitive subjects reached the $11\ \mu\text{s}$ threshold reported by Klumpp and Eady. The other three participants had threshold ITDs between 16 and $36\ \mu\text{s}$. This raises questions regarding subject selection and exclusion criteria in the 1950s studies.

One last relevant change over the decades has been the amount of detail provided about study participants. Neither age range nor hearing status were reported in the historic studies. Bernstein and Trahiotis (2016) have tested dichotic

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tone-in-noise detection in clinically normal hearing subjects. Detection thresholds depended significantly on the accurately and repeatedly measured audiometric threshold at 4 KHz. This suggests that using conventional audiogram testing and “clinically normal hearing” as inclusion criterion is potentially too coarse.

With respect to the question, “What is the smallest ITD normal hearing humans can detect?,” the current state of the literature can be summarized by two main points. First, all studies consistently report lowest thresholds near 10 μ s for noise stimuli or complex stimuli (Klumpp and Eady, 1956, Mills 1958) and just above 10 μ s for pure tones (Brughera *et al.*, 2013). Second, the most comprehensive studies on the subject are from the 1950s. This is, of course, not a problem, but a variety of presentation methods and reporting standards have changed during the intervening 60 years, some of which may impact conclusions.

With respect to the question, “Which stimulus maximizes ITD sensitivity?,” it can be summarized that frequencies between 500 and 1000 Hz are essential (Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956), and noise is likely to yield lower thresholds than pure tones would (Klumpp and Eady, 1956).

The objectives of the current study were to determine systematically the stimulus and experimental paradigm that results in the smallest threshold ITDs for well-trained and un-trained normal hearing listeners (experiment 1), and to provide an accurate threshold ITD reference value (experiment 2).

II. EXPERIMENT 1: IDENTIFICATION OF STIMULUS AND PROCEDURE THAT MAXIMIZE ITD SENSITIVITY

A. Approach

Seven stimulus parameters and procedure types were identified that have either been shown to influence ITD sensitivity or that differed across studies. Parameters and stimuli that have been shown previously to yield poor sensitivity and, thus, not be ideal for ITD discrimination were not included. The tested parameters were: (1) stimulus waveform, (2) level, (3) stimulus duration, (4) interstimulus interval, (5) inclusion versus exclusion of stimulus onset and offset ITD, (6) constant stimulus presentation versus an adaptive staircase procedure, and (7) inclusion versus exclusion of diotic “cuing” intervals. Details on the stimuli are presented in Sec. II B 3 and details on all procedures in Sec. II B 4.

A complete examination of the seven-dimensional parameter space would result in too many conditions to conduct experimentally on participants. To reduce the number of conditions, arguably the most important parameter, “stimulus waveform,” was tested first. Then, the best stimuli from the stimulus waveform tests were chosen for further testing by varying one of the other six parameters to identify the optimal presentation technique.

B. Methods

1. Participants

Participants were limited to young adults (18–39 years) with audiometric thresholds equal to or less than 10 dB

hearing level (HL) at octave spaced frequencies from 125 to 8000 Hz. One reason for this strict inclusion criterion is that it has been shown recently that subjects with a slight (sub-clinical) hearing loss have a reduced binaural release from masking (Bernstein and Trahiotis, 2016). To minimize a potential confound through slight hearing loss this criterion was included.

A total of nine normal-hearing trained subjects aged between 18 and 38 years (average age = 23, F = 6, M = 3) each participated in the experiment for between 15 to 19 h. The interaural asymmetry in audiometric threshold was generally less or equal 5 dB at any of the frequencies tested. A 10 dB difference only occurred once at 4000 Hz for subject 9. Audiometric pure tone averages (PTA) ranged from -2.5 to $+5.3$ dB HL. Left-right PTA asymmetry ranged from 0 to 3.1 dB (average 1.4 dB). Two of the nine participants were lab members and were well informed about the purpose and methods of the study and did not receive any extra compensation. The other seven participants were compensated on an hourly basis. Five other volunteers were not included for two different reasons: Two individuals had threshold ITDs that increased throughout the practice runs, and they self-reported concentration problems. The other three individuals had one or more audiometric thresholds higher than 10 dB HL.

2. Apparatus

Stimuli were generated digitally in MATLAB (MathWorks, Natick, MA, United States) using the AFC software package (Ewert, 2013) for MATLAB and presented via a Focusrite Scarlett 2i2 2 In/2 Out USB sound card, a HB7 TDT headphone driver, and ER-2 tubephone insert earphones (Etymotic Research, Inc., El Grove Village, IL, United States) to the subject seating in a double walled sound booth. The left and right ER-2 insert earphones were calibrated at 800 Hz, without any frequency-dependent correction.

3. Stimuli

Three different types of stimuli were tested in this experiment: Pure tones, tone complexes, and noises.

a. Pure tones. The first stimulus type was a pure tone,

$$s(t) = \sin(2\pi ft).$$

Pure tones with three different frequencies were tested separately in this experiment: 600, 800, and 1000 Hz. Tones are the most basic and fundamental class of stimuli and have been used frequently in ITD experiments. The frequency range was chosen based on consistent reports that the range of best sensitivity to ITD is between 600–1000 Hz (Brughera *et al.*, 2013; Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956; Klumpp and Eady, 1956).

b. Tone complexes. The second stimulus type was a tone complex, i.e., multiple pure tones, added in cosine phase,

$$s_{TC}(t) = [\cos(2\pi f_1 t)] + [\cos(2\pi f_2 t)] + \dots + [\cos(2\pi f_n t)].$$

Three different tone complexes were tested in this experiment: 100–1400 Hz with 100-Hz component intervals, 600–1000 Hz with 100-Hz component intervals, and 600–1000 Hz with 20-Hz component intervals. The cosine phase offers a steep envelope, which may provide an additional ITD cue. The cosine phase also offers the interpretation of this class of stimuli as filtered click-trains.

Previous studies did not systematically investigate tone complexes. The three different complexes were chosen to cover the complete range of temporal fine-structure (TFS) ITD sensitivity (up to 1400 Hz) or just the range of best ITD sensitivity (Brughera *et al.*, 2013). In terms of the latter 600–1000 Hz range, there were two different conditions: one with 100-Hz component spacing and one with 20-Hz spacing. With 100-Hz spacing, each component stimulates mostly independent auditory filters (Glasberg and Moore, 1990), and information may be integrated across filters for better performance compared to pure tones. With 20-Hz component intervals, a very homogenous spectral excitation in the most sensitive frequency region is provided, as occurs with noise stimuli, but still with a deterministic waveform. We hypothesized that either feature may provide very good ITD sensitivity.

c. Noises. The third stimulus type was noise. Five different noises were tested in this experiment: 600–1000 Hz band-pass, 750–850 Hz band-pass, 20–1400 Hz band-pass, 20–20 000 Hz broadband white noise, and 20–20 000 Hz broadband pink noise. Band-pass filtering was performed in the frequency domain by setting the amplitudes of all components outside of the pass band to zero.

As with tone complexes, the 600–1000 Hz frequency range was chosen because it is the frequency region yielding the highest ITD sensitivity (Brughera *et al.*, 2013), and 20–1400 Hz was chosen because it covers the complete fine-structure-sensitive region. In addition, a 750–850 Hz band-pass was chosen because this approximates a single auditory filter centered near the most sensitive region. Last, two conditions covering the complete audible spectrum (20–20 000 Hz) were also chosen for this experiment: pink and white noise. First, pink noise provides an equal amount of energy per octave and therefore a relatively homogeneous excitation of all auditory filters. Surprisingly, to our knowledge, pink noise has not been used in previous studies on ITD sensitivity. In contrast, white noise provides a relatively large amount of energy to the high frequency filters, for which no TFS ITD sensitivity is expected.

For all three stimulus types, the default level was 70 dB sound pressure level (SPL), default duration was 0.5 s including 50-ms squared-cosine onset and offset gating, and the default interstimulus interval was 0.3 s. The ITD was applied either prior to gating (default: excluding onset and offset ITD) or after gating (included onset and offset ITD). For the default “ongoing ITD” case, it is most effective and precise to generate the ITD by a phase shift of each frequency component. However, for including onset and offset ITD, this is not straight-forward, and generating the delay in the time-domain is easier. However, the latter comes at the

cost of ITD discretization into multiples of digital sample duration. For typical sampling frequencies below 100 KHz, the ITD step size is $>10 \mu\text{s}$, which is unacceptable for measuring thresholds of the same order of magnitude. To reduce the discretization confound, stimuli were sampled with a rate of 1 MHz to allow for an ITD precision of $1 \mu\text{s}$ and then down-sampled to 48 kHz for presentation. To avoid a change in generation method, the ongoing ITD conditions were also generated in the time domain.

d. Other stimulus variations. In addition to varying the stimulus waveform, other stimulus parameters were manipulated. For measuring the influence of stimulus level on threshold ITD, three different sound levels of 60, 70, 80 dB SPL were tested. This range was chosen, because it has previously been reported to yield the lowest threshold ITDs (Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956).

Furthermore, the influence of stimulus duration was tested. ITD thresholds decrease with increasing duration; typically, up to about 0.5 s duration (McFadden and Sharpley, 1972). Only Tobias and Zerlin (1959) report an additional small decrease between 0.5 and 0.7 s. Recent typical durations are 0.3 s (e.g., Bernstein and Trahiotis, 2009) to 0.5 s (e.g., Brughera *et al.*, 2013). In contrast, Klumpp and Eady (1956) used 2 s. Based on Tobias and Zerlin (1959) it is possible that this longer duration is one of the reasons for the lower threshold reported by Klumpp and Eady (1956). However, in pilot experiments we compared 0.5 with 2.0 s and identified the 2.0 s duration to yield higher thresholds and to be more exhausting. We therefore decided to compare 0.5 against 1.0 s in the formal experiment (1.0 s was also used by Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956).

The last comparison investigated whether the inclusion of stimulus onset and offset ITDs using 50-ms squared-cosine onset and offset gating improved performance. Almost all studies on the subject in recent decades excluded onset and offset ITD, because it isolates the ongoing TFS ITD cue from the transient ITD cue. Buell and colleagues (Buell and Hafter, 1991; Buell *et al.*, 1991) showed that ongoing TFS ITD typically dominates perception. All this speaks in favor of excluding onset ITD and only reporting lowest TFS ITD thresholds. On the other hand, if there was any impact of adding an onset ITD to an ongoing ITD it can be expected to be an improvement. Klumpp and Eady (1956) also included onset and offset ITDs but their even longer gating times of 0.3 s, likely rendered the transient ITD information very weak. Nevertheless, this condition was included for the sake of completeness, and it was hypothesized that the “onset ITD included” condition would be equally good or marginally better than the “ongoing alone” condition. In theory, a short steep onset can be expected to yield the strongest improvement. However, with our focus on ongoing (TFS) ITD we refrained from systematically changing onset parameters.

4. Procedure

The default procedure was a two-interval two alternative forced choice task (two-interval 2 AFC). In each trial the subjects were asked, “Which interval was perceived the most

toward the right-hand side?” Subjects responded by pressing the corresponding target interval number on a standard computer keyboard. Visual feedback was provided after each trial. The target interval had a right-leading ITD that was half of the nominal ITD, whereas the reference interval had a left-leading ITD that was half of the nominal ITD. The symmetric presentation minimizes any potential hemispheric effects and ensures that the subject cannot perform the task based on changes in interaural coherence (Dietz *et al.*, 2012).

An adaptive “three-down, one-up” staircase procedure was chosen, i.e., the ITD was decreased after three correct responses and increased after one wrong response. Theoretically, this method estimates the 79.4% correct level on the psychometric function (Levitt, 1971). Each adaptive track started at an ITD of 40 μ s, which was expected to be above threshold. The initial step-size was a factor of 2, which was reduced to 1.414 and 1.189 after the first and second “down-up reversal,” respectively. An adaptive track was terminated after six reversals at the minimum step-size, i.e., a total of 9 to 10 reversals. Multiplicative changing of the ITD was employed, because it has been shown that threshold distributions are approximately Gaussian on the logarithmic ITD scale (Yost *et al.*, 1974; Saberi, 1995).

The first procedural comparison was between the default adaptive staircase procedure and a constant stimulus procedure. For the latter, eight fixed ITDs (2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 14, 20, and 28 μ s) were presented 100 times each. Presentation was in four blocks, with each block consisting of 25 presentations at the same ITD, followed by the next smaller ITD. The constant stimulus procedure was utilized in the above-mentioned 1950s studies. Potentially this may result in better performance compared to the adaptive staircase procedure; however, it was shown not to make a difference in binaural detection tasks (Trahiotis *et al.*, 1990).

The second procedural comparison was between the default two-interval 2 AFC and a four-interval 2 AFC task (Bernstein and Trahiotis, 1994). In the four-interval 2 AFC task, the target ITD was presented in either the second or third interval, while the first and fourth intervals had zero ITD (“cuing intervals”). Bernstein and Trahiotis (1994) reported that the four-interval method was more reliable, at least in cases of target uncertainty. On the other hand, the two-interval method is twice as fast in terms of the presentation time. Furthermore, if there is more than one interval for L/R discrimination, it is commonly performed as a motion task (Yost *et al.*, 1974). For a motion task, a two-interval procedure may be more natural, because it simplifies the task to essentially discriminating rightwards from leftwards movement. On the other hand, in the four-interval procedure, subjects can discriminate between the intervals in which the movement occurs, but do not have a single direction of movement. It remains to be shown which procedure results in lower threshold ITDs. For the four-interval task, a hemispherically balanced presentation, as in the two-interval procedure, is not possible in the same way. Therefore, the ITD was applied in full to the target interval (always right leading) whereas the other three intervals were diotic.

In the last comparison, the interstimulus interval was varied. While 0.3 s is a typical value for this parameter, in

our pilot experiments we had the impression that a shorter interstimulus interval might result in a better sensitivity. We therefore added an interstimulus interval of 50 ms condition to our test battery.

As part 1 of this experiment, the eleven different waveform conditions were measured in six runs and in randomized order. The second run of any condition could only appear after the first run was completed for all conditions. After we measured thresholds for the eleven stimuli for the first six of the nine subjects, the two stimuli yielding the lowest thresholds were selected as “presumably optimal” because their threshold ITD only differed by 0.2 μ s.

In part 2 of this experiment, the influence of the three other stimulus variations (level, duration, and onset/offset ITD) and of the three procedural comparisons were investigated. The stimulus parameters and the procedures from part 1 were set as default values and only one of the six parameters was varied at a time. For stimulus level there were two non-default values: 60 and 80 dB SPL. The default condition—identical to part 1—was re-measured here as the 70 dB SPL condition. For each of the other five parameters there was only one non-default value. Effects of the six parameters were measured in blocks of three runs in this order: (1) inclusion of onset and offset ITD, (2) stimulus levels (60, 70, 80 dB SPL), (3) constant stimulus procedure, (4) stimulus duration (1 s), (5) interstimulus interval (0.05 s), and (6) four-interval 2 AFC procedure. After the first three runs were measured, an additional three runs were measured in the reversed order.

The participants were trained by giving practice blocks identical to the actual experiment to avoid large training effects during the actual data collection. During the first session, subjects received at least 30 min of training before the formal data collection began. In all subsequent sessions, participants were given one practice run before continuing the formal data collection.

5. Data analysis methods

Individual thresholds were derived from reconstructing the psychometric functions from the adaptive tracks and subsequent fitting. The reason for using psychometric fits over the commonly used adaptive track reversal average was because reversals are prone to substantial bias and less precision (García-Pérez, 1998; Schlauch and Rose, 1990). For comparison, we also included the conventional reversal analysis later in experiment 2, where the bias becomes evident (see Sec. IV). Psychometric functions were estimated using a parametric fit of a Weibull function to all responses from all six runs. This includes the first presentations of a run, where the step-size is large. Specific for a 2 AFC procedure with 50% chance level and threshold T defined as the 79.4% correct level, the estimated correct rate (y) can be expressed as a function of ITD,

$$y(\text{ITD}) = 1 - (1/2)e^{-0.8853 \times (\text{ITD}/T)^s}.$$

The two free parameters were the slope (s) and threshold ITD (T). The constant 0.8853 is a result of the specific

chance and threshold levels. The maximum likelihood fit was derived by a two-dimensional “brute-force search.” Thresholds were sampled in $0.25 \mu\text{s}$ steps and slopes in steps of 0.05.

Across-subject averages were derived through geometric mean and geometric standard deviation. Accordingly, all analyses of variance (ANOVA) were conducted on the logarithm of the individual threshold ITDs.

C. Results

1. Stimulus waveform

Geometric mean threshold ITDs were derived from the individual thresholds for each of the eleven stimulus waveforms (Fig. 1). Note that the threshold ITD ordinate in Fig. 1 is logarithmic, as a consequence of the threshold ITD distributions being approximately Gaussian on a logarithmic scale (Sabeti, 1995).

The three pure tone stimuli yielded the highest threshold ITDs (Fig. 1) with averages between $22 \mu\text{s}$ (800 Hz) and $27 \mu\text{s}$ (600 Hz). The 600–1000 Hz noise and 20–1400 Hz noise yielded the lowest threshold ITDs of 10.0 and $10.7 \mu\text{s}$, respectively. Both narrower and wider bandwidths resulted in higher thresholds. The ITD sensitivity for tone complexes was higher than for pure tones but lower than for noise of the same bandwidth. Best threshold ITDs for this stimulus class were $14 \mu\text{s}$ for both stimuli with $f_0 = 100 \text{ Hz}$.

A repeated measure one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) on the log-scaled threshold ITD data revealed a significant main effect of stimulus waveform [$F(10,88) = 9.75$; $p < 0.001$]. A *post hoc* pairwise comparison (Tukey) revealed a significant difference (assuming $\alpha = 0.05$) between threshold ITDs for two pure-tone stimuli with the highest thresholds (600 and 1000 Hz) and all stimuli from the other two classes. Thresholds for the 800 Hz pure tone were significantly higher than for the two tone complexes with $f_0 = 100 \text{ Hz}$, and the 600–1000 Hz and 20–1400 Hz noises. No other pairs differed significantly.

Because the conservative ANOVA *post hoc* test did not reveal any most ITD sensitive condition, or a small group of most sensitive conditions, a rank comparison was conducted. For eight of the nine subjects 600–1000 Hz noise was among the two most sensitive conditions, as was 20–1400 Hz noise for seven of nine subjects. Thus, in only three of 18 instances were any of the remaining seven conditions among the two most sensitive. For all nine subjects one of the two above-mentioned noise conditions was among the two most sensitive. Therefore, we proceeded to test the other parameters with these two stimuli.

2. Other parameters

In this section, the isolated influence of the other test parameters and procedural differences on threshold ITD are analyzed. Figure 2 (level) and Fig. 3 (other parameters) show individual threshold ITDs together with the across-subject geometric means for the two “best” stimulus waveforms. When comparing the default condition data from the two separate measurements, thresholds for the 600–1000 Hz noise increased

FIG. 1. Threshold ITDs for the eleven different stimulus waveforms using a stimulus level of 70 dB SPL, stimulus duration of 0.5 s, an interstimulus interval of 0.3 s, the two-interval paradigm, a three-down one-up adaptive procedure, and excluded onset and offset ITD. The data points indicate the geometric mean across the nine participants, and the error bars indicate the geometric standard errors.

by $1 \mu\text{s}$ whereas thresholds for the 20–1400 Hz noise decreased by $1 \mu\text{s}$. For the four comparisons with other parameters (Fig. 3) the data from the default condition data were reused.

First, the influence of stimulus level (60, 70, 80 dB SPL) on threshold ITD is reported (Fig. 2). While threshold ITDs at 70 dB SPL were marginally lower than at 60 and 80 dB SPL, a repeated measures two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) on the log-scaled ITD data revealed no significant main effect of level [$F(2,48) = 0.52$; $p = 0.599$] and noise stimulus type [$F(1,48) = 0.18$; $p = 0.669$]. There was no interaction between level and noise stimulus type [$F(2,48) = 0.12$; $p = 0.888$].

Next, we investigated whether thresholds change when adding onset and offset ITDs [Fig. 3(a)]. Both visual

FIG. 2. (Color online) Threshold ITD as a function of stimulus level for the two stimuli that resulted in lowest threshold ITD in part 1. The symbols indicate the geometric mean across the nine participants (600–1000 Hz band pass filtered noise: circles, 20–1400 Hz noise: diamonds). The error bars indicate the geometric standard errors. Individual thresholds are plotted as thin lines.

FIG. 3. (Color online) Comparisons of the influence of four experimental parameters on threshold ITD. The default condition data (70 dB SPL, onset ITD excluded, duration 0.5 s, 2 intervals, 0.3 s pause) were reused in all four panels. Same format as Fig. 2: 20–1400 Hz filtered noise as diamonds, 600–1000 Hz noise as circles. (a) Threshold ITD for transient onset and offset ITDs included versus excluded. (b) Threshold ITD for two different stimulus durations. (c) Comparison of threshold ITD for the default two-interval and a four-interval 2 AFC task. (d) Threshold ITD as a function of interstimulus interval.

inspection and an ANOVA on the log-ITD data revealed no significant main effect of onset and offset ITD excluded versus included [$F(1,32) = 0.04$; $p = 0.846$] or noise stimulus type [$F(1,32) = 0.52$; $p = 0.477$], as well as no interaction [$F(1,32) = 0$; $p = 0.948$].

Third, a potential influence of stimulus duration was investigated [Fig. 3(b)]. For the longer (1 s) stimulus duration, average thresholds increased by $1.5 \mu\text{s}$ for the 20–1400 Hz noise and by $0.9 \mu\text{s}$ for the 600–1000 Hz noise. An ANOVA on the log-scaled ITD data revealed neither a significant main effect of stimulus duration [$F(1,32) = 1.36$; $p = 0.252$], nor of noise stimulus type [$F(1,32) = 0.24$; $p = 0.625$], and there was no significant interaction [$F(1,32) = 0.08$; $p = 0.777$].

Fourth, we examined whether the addition of cuing intervals influenced threshold ITDs. Figure 3(c) reveals that the cuing intervals increased threshold ITDs by $1.7 \mu\text{s}$ for the 600–1000 Hz noise and by $3.9 \mu\text{s}$ for the 20–1400 Hz noise. An ANOVA revealed a significant main effect of the number of intervals [$F(1,32) = 5.31$; $p = 0.028$], but not of noise stimulus type [$F(1,32) = 0.01$; $p = 0.941$], as well as no interaction [$F(1,32) = 0.4$; $p = 0.532$].

Threshold ITD as a function of the interstimulus interval is shown in Fig. 3(d). An ANOVA revealed no significant main effect of interstimulus interval [$F(1,32) = 0.16$; $p = 0.691$]. The influence of noise stimulus type [$F(1,32) = 0.21$; $p = 0.648$], and the two-factor interaction [$F(1,32) = 0.19$; $p = 0.669$] also were not significant.

Finally, a constant-stimulus procedure was conducted with default parameters: stimulus level of 70 dB SPL, stimulus duration of 0.5 s, interstimulus interval of 0.3 s, two-interval paradigm, 2 AFC procedure, and excluded onset and offset ITD. Percent correct values for the eight fixed ITD values (2.5 to

$28.3 \mu\text{s}$ in half-octave step sizes) were averaged across nine participants for the two noise stimuli (Fig. 4). For the 600–1000 Hz noise, ITDs of 6, 8, and $10 \mu\text{s}$ resulted in 70%, 76%, and 79% correct, respectively. The corresponding percent correct rates for the 20–1400 Hz noise were 70%, 75%, and 78% correct. Thus, for both noises, an ITD of $6 \mu\text{s}$ would be virtually identical to the threshold yielded by a 70.7% 2-down, 1-up procedure and an ITD of $10 \mu\text{s}$ virtually identical to the threshold yielded by a 79.4% 3-down, 1-up procedure. The ITD of $10 \mu\text{s}$ is almost identical to the threshold yielded by the 79.4% correct from the adaptive procedure (e.g., Fig. 2 and $10 \mu\text{s}$ at 70 dB SPL).

Visual inspection of the individual psychometric functions obtained with the adaptive (three-down, one-up, 2 AFC) and constant stimulus procedure (Fig. 5), revealed no systematic differences. One subject (S6) appears to perform better with the adaptive procedure, while subject S7 is the other way around.

D. Discussion

The objective of Experiment 1 was to determine the stimulus and method that yielded the smallest threshold ITD, i.e., the maximum ITD sensitivity. While drawing upon Klumpp and Eady's (1956) methods, the current experiment was created to revisit the topic more systematically and extensively, using methods that have become more common over the past 20–30 years.

The only statistically significant influences on threshold ITD were found when the stimulus waveform was changed and when cuing intervals were added. In line with the qualitative evidence from Klumpp and Eady (1956), pure tones do not produce the lowest possible thresholds. The differences are even more pronounced in the current study and the pure tone threshold ITDs compare better to the data from Brughera *et al.* (2013). Stimuli with a broader spectrum covering several auditory filters including the 800-Hz region resulted in significantly better sensitivity. As all other

FIG. 4. (Color online) Percent correct rate for the test stimuli as a function of ITD obtained from the constant stimulus procedure. The symbols (600–1000 Hz band pass filtered noise: circles, 20–1400 Hz noise: diamonds) indicate the arithmetic mean across the nine participants, i.e., 900 responses per data point. Individual data are plotted as thin lines.

FIG. 5. (Color online) Individual psychometric functions for the two different types of procedures (adaptive and constant stimulus). Data only shown for the 20–1400 Hz noise. The nine panels portray individual correct rates of the nine participants (S1–S9). Data from the adaptive (three-down one-up, 2 AFC) procedure is indicated by black diamonds with error bars that denote the 95% confidence level derived from the binomial distribution. Therefore, confidence interval size depends on the average %-correct and on the number of times measured. Only data from ITDs presented at least 15 times during the six adaptive tracks are plotted. The correct rates obtained with the constant stimulus procedure are indicated as asterisks. For the constant stimulus procedure, the size of the error bar does not depend on the number of presentations because it is constant at a value of 100. To avoid overcrowded panels, the error bars for constant stimulus procedure are not plotted. The constant stimulus procedure's 95% confidence intervals increase from $\pm 5\%$ (at 90% correct rate) to $\pm 8\%$ (at 50% correct rate). The solid lines indicate the respective Weibull function fits.

differences were not significant at an $\alpha = 0.05$ level, some of the trends will be briefly discussed:

Participants performed slightly better with tone complexes than with the pure tones with average thresholds across the nine participants well-below $20 \mu\text{s}$. It was expected that the three tone complexes would provide very high ITD sensitivity, because they cover not just one but all the most ITD-sensitive frequency bands. It was unclear if the deterministic nature of tonal complexes would yield an advantage over noise. Ultimately, the average thresholds were slightly higher than the corresponding noise.

When comparing the results obtained with different noises, the narrow-band 100-Hz wide noise, centered at the most ITD-sensitive region of 800 Hz did not produce the lowest thresholds. Again, in line with speculation as to why tone-complexes provide better ITD sensitivity than pure tones, maximum sensitivity appears to require integration of information across multiple auditory filters.

The two broadband noises resulted in higher threshold ITDs compared to the two intermediately broad low-frequency noises. A possible explanation could be that broad-band conditions simply have less energy in the TFS frequency region and ITD sensitivity is level-dependent (Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956). From our data, we have indirect evidence that level dependence is likely not the main effect: our experiment in which level was varied revealed almost no level dependence in

the 60–80 dB SPL interval. For the 20–1400 Hz noise, 60 dB SPL corresponds to a spectrum level of 29 dB. The spectrum level of the 70 dB SPL broadband white noise was very similar at 27 dB. The pink noise with same RMS level did not have a constant spectrum level but it was even >30 dB in the 800 Hz region. Because we found no level dependence for the filtered noise, and because of the similar spectral level, it can be speculated that the slightly poorer performance obtained with the two broadband noises is not the result of lower spectrum level.

The similarity of thresholds from the 600–1000 Hz and the 20–1400 Hz conditions hint that TFS sensitive frequencies outside of the 600–1000 Hz region neither harm nor substantially improve ITD sensitivity. Across all conditions and secondary parameters tested, on average, subjects had slightly lower thresholds with the 20–1400 Hz noise. This stimulus is also very similar to the 150–1700 Hz band-pass filtered noise that resulted in the lowest average threshold ITD reported in the literature (Klumpp and Eady, 1956). The possibility remains that a bandwidth intermediate to the two tested conditions produces the lowest thresholds. Dedicated high precision measurements with many subjects would be required to measure these sub-microsecond differences.

Somewhat expectedly, both including and excluding onset and offset ITD resulted in equally good sensitivity. Although our focus remains on ongoing TFS ITD, we speculate that shorter gating ramp times could, potentially, improve sensitivity, but not substantially (see e.g., Buell *et al.*, 1991). Because our focus is on ongoing TFS ITD, we leave the discussion of this parameter with this short note.

A less expected outcome was the worsening of performance when including the cuing intervals [Fig. 3(c)]. Bernstein and Trahiotis (1982, 1994, 2009, 2016) routinely add the cuing intervals, likely because they improve thresholds in cases of stimulus uncertainty (Bernstein and Trahiotis, 1994). Stimulus uncertainty was not expected here, so the hypothesis was that the cuing intervals would neither improve nor worsen ITD sensitivity. A possible explanation for the significantly higher threshold ITDs with cuing intervals in the present study is that ITD discrimination can be measured by proxy of a L/R motion direction discrimination task (Yost *et al.*, 1974). It appears plausible that a L/R motion discrimination task is most directly measured with a two-interval procedure. We speculate that our participants likely utilized this perception of movement concept and that the higher thresholds in the four-interval paradigm could have been caused by a reduced ability to exploit the movement cue. This argument notwithstanding, there is a potential small confound in that our participants were more familiar with the two-interval procedure. Therefore, we tested the first three runs of the four-interval procedure last. Because runs 4–6 were measured in reversed order, the four-interval procedure was effectively measured in 6 consecutive runs and subjects did not have to switch back and forth. In our $N=2$ pilot experiments, the situation was, however, reversed. We used the four-interval procedure exclusively for several hours of testing, and threshold ITDs decreased directly after leaving out the cuing intervals.

When comparing the constant stimulus data with the geometric mean of the last six reversals of the adaptive

tracks (our initial approach—not shown in this experiment), we found the average of reversals to correspond to the 76% correct value, rather than to the expected 79.4% correct value. To clarify if the subjects performed differently or if there was an analysis confound, we reconstructed psychometric functions from the adaptive tracks. Figure 5 clearly shows that—on average—subjects perform virtually identically. In contrast, we found that the bias of the reversal averaging was as large as 3.5%-points or 1–2 μ s in threshold ITD. Therefore, we changed the analysis method to fitting of the psychometric function throughout this study. This offered the additional advantage of reporting different %-correct thresholds and the slope of the psychometric function. It also allowed us to include all experimental trials in the calculation of the threshold, which resulted in greater precision. Through additional analysis of simulated data, we became aware that the bias results from the choice of step size, the starting value of the adaptive track, and—most importantly—from the trial after which the step size is reduced. We reduced the step size during “down-up” reversals and effectively measured the 76% correct value. When reducing the step size during “up-down” reversals, the simulated thresholds corresponded to the 81% or 82% correct value. The difference becomes smaller with an increased number of reversals, but this is challenging for the subjects. Rather than changing the step size after a specific type of reversal, as it is commonly done in many monaural and some binaural studies, others (e.g., Bernstein and Trahiotis, 2009, 2016) changed the step size after a fixed number of reversals of any kind, partially cancelling out the bias. In retrospect, we see a small advantage of the “fixed number” method, but when the start value is near the 100% correct mark, both methods become virtually identical and produce the same bias. Fortunately, reconstructing the psychometric function allows for a bias-free analysis of the data independent of the reversal strategy employed.

III. EXPERIMENT 2: ACCURATE MEASUREMENT OF THE SMALLEST THRESHOLD ITD

A. Objective and approach

The purpose of this experiment was to obtain a highly accurate measure of threshold ITD from the chosen condition identified in the previous experiment. Thresholds are reported for both trained and un-trained young normal hearing listeners.

It can be argued that we already have the data for the trained listeners from experiment 1. On the other hand, when the study was designed, it was not clear if several deviations from the default condition would result in lower thresholds and we would then measure a new combination of parameters here that was not tested before. Furthermore, experiment 1 was very long and somewhat tedious for the subjects. Experiment 1 was designed to average out any order, training, or fatigue effects. It cannot be claimed that subjects cannot perform better when they are fully trained and need to perform only one short measurement.

B. Methods

1. Participants

In this experiment, there were two pools of participants. The first pool consisted of the nine trained normal hearing listeners from experiment 1. The second pool consisted of 53 un-trained normal hearing listeners aged between 18 and 39 years (average age = 25, F = 33, M = 20) who participated in the experiment for approximately 30 min. A less restrictive inclusion criterion was chosen for the un-trained listeners: They were required to have absolute thresholds equal or less than 20 dB HL for 750 and 4000 Hz in each ear. The frequency of 750 Hz was chosen, because it is close to the best ITD sensitivity of 800 Hz (Brughera *et al.*, 2013). The frequency of 4000 Hz was chosen, because it is more indicative of hearing loss. One of 54 subjects was excluded because of this criterion. The participants performed the entire experiment in one session and were compensated at its conclusion. To our knowledge, all participants in this experiment were university students and had no prior participation in any binaural hearing tests.

2. Apparatus and stimuli

The apparatus was the same as in experiment 1.

The stimulus utilized in this experiment was the 20–1400 Hz band-pass noise. This stimulus was selected because, for the most part, it produced the lowest thresholds in experiment 1. The stimulus was presented at 70 dB SPL with a duration of 0.5 s, and an interstimulus interval of 0.05 s, using the two-interval procedure and excluding onset and offset ITD.

To provide a higher ITD presentation accuracy, the internal sampling rate was increased to 6.144 MHz, allowing for an ITD step size of 0.16 μ s. The stimulus was presented with a 96 kHz sampling rate.

3. Procedure

A two-interval 2 AFC task was employed, identical to that employed in experiment 1. The only parameter that was changed was the starting value of ITD. Rather than 40 μ s it was now 41.67 μ s for the trained listeners, corresponding to exactly four samples at 96 KHz. For the un-trained listeners, the starting value was 83.33 μ s.

The trained listeners were tested with this condition for nine adaptive runs after two practice runs that were identical to the actual experiment. Training was included, because for some subjects several weeks had passed since they had completed experiment 1. Subjects were instructed that this was the final test in which we assumed that thresholds were going to be quite low. They were given the option of viewing their threshold after each run and to compare that to their own threshold from experiment 1. All subjects opted to view their thresholds. Viewing their thresholds after each run may have promoted motivation and potentially reduced the thresholds in comparison to those obtained from experiment 1. The duration of this single session was always less than one hour.

For the un-trained listeners, the approach was explicitly to avoid training in ITD discrimination prior to data collection. They were given one run of a threshold ILD (interaural level difference) task to become accustomed to the two-interval 2

FIG. 6. Left-right discrimination as a function of ITD for the 20–1400 Hz noise with an interstimulus interval of 50 ms. The nine panels portray individual data of the nine participants (S1–S9). The darker colored curve is the Weibull function fit to the data. Percent correct rates are only shown for ITDs that were presented at least 15 times. The error bars denote the 95% confidence level, which decreases with the number of presentations and with an increasing correct rate. The vertical dashed line indicates the threshold ITD at the 79.4% correct rate. The performance change (experiment 2 threshold minus experiment 1 threshold) is indicated at the lower right corner of each panel.

AFC adaptive procedure and to left-right discrimination. They were tested for only five runs to make sure that the data were collected before they had even 30 min of experience in the task.

C. Results

1. Trained listeners

A Weibull function was fitted to the data in the same way as in experiment 1. Data are shown together with the

TABLE I. Summary of threshold ITDs from the fitted psychometric functions at different percent correct rates and slopes. In addition, conventionally calculated geometric means of the reversals are shown. The threshold difference between the 75% and 76% correct thresholds is stated as a measurement of how much more ITD is required to increase the correct responses by 1% point near the steepest slope. Next the slope of the psychometric function is shown as the reciprocal value of the threshold difference. Last, for trained listeners, the %-correct rate at 10.4 μ s ITD (1 sample at 96 KHz) is given in the rightmost column. For most of the un-trained listeners, the adaptive procedure did not collect enough data at 10.4 μ s, so no %-correct score can be derived. By default, averages are the geometric mean.

Subject #	Threshold ITD (μ s)					Inverse slope (76% threshold—75% threshold) in μ s	Slope (%-correct change per μ s)	% correct at 10.4 μ s
	@ 70.7%	@ 75%	@ 76% ($d' = 1$)	@ 79.4%	From reversal			
1	6.1	7.7	8.0	9.6	9.3	0.44	2.3	81
2	5.6	7.0	7.4	8.7	8.8	0.41	2.5	83
3	4.3	4.8	5.0	5.6	5.1	0.18	5.6	96
4	6.4	7.9	8.3	9.7	7.8	0.38	2.6	81
5	5.5	6.9	7.2	8.5	8.0	0.39	2.5	83
6	8.7	11.4	12.2	14.8	10.8	0.69	1.5	73
7	6.0	7.4	7.7	9.0	7.6	0.35	2.9	83
8	3.3	4.0	4.2	4.8	4.2	0.18	5.4	96
9	6.1	7.0	7.2	8.0	6.6	0.25	4.0	88
Average	5.6	6.9	7.2	8.3	7.3	0.33	3.3 ^a	85 ^a
Standard error (%)	10.5	11.6	11.9	12.8	11.5	18.2	14.8	2.9
Un-trained listeners								
Average	14.6	18.1	19.0	22.1	19.6	0.83	1.4 ^a	
Standard error (%)	8.0	7.6	7.5	7.6	7.3	10.1	6.5	

^aArithmetic means.

fits in Fig. 6 and summarized in Table I. It can be seen that the most ITD-sensitive subject (S8) responded to an ITD of 3.7 μ s with 80% correct (44 out of 55 presentations). At the same ITD, subject S4 responded with 68% correct.

Threshold ITDs at four different percent correct rates were derived from the fitted psychometric function (Table I) for the nine participants: a 70.7% correct rate for comparison with many studies that used a 2-down, 1-up procedure, a 75% correct rate to compare with most of the historic thresholds (especially Klumpp and Eady, 1956; Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956), a 76% correct rate, which corresponds to $d' = 1$, and a 79.4% correct rate for a comparison with 3-down, 1-up data, including the internal comparison with the reversal data. Note that the average threshold from the reversals is 7.3 μ s, which is supposed to reflect the 79.4% correct level. In contrast, the fit results in 8.3 μ s at the 79.4% correct level, and 7.3 μ s closely corresponds to 7.2 μ s at the 76% correct level.

The relative standard error of the mean was always between 10% and 13%. As a result of the geometric averaging, only the relative error can be stated precisely. A conservative transformation into μ s, by using the larger upper portion of the confidence interval, translates into a standard error smaller than 1 μ s at all percent correct levels stated in Table I.

Across the nine participants, a 1% difference (between 75% and 76%) corresponded to an increase in threshold ITD of 0.33 μ s. Conversely, a difference of 1 μ s ITD, on average, caused the percent correct rate to change 3% points near the steepest slope, e.g., from 75% to 78%.

2. Un-trained listeners

Of the 53 un-trained listeners tested, 52 had threshold ITDs derived from Weibull fits at the 79.4% correct level (Fig. 7) for the 20–1400 Hz noise stimulus described in Sec.

FIG. 7. Histogrammic representation of the 79.4% correct level threshold ITDs for 52 un-trained participants using 20–1400 Hz noise presented at 70 dB SPL with an interstimulus interval of 50 ms.

III B 2. The average (geometric mean) threshold ITD at the 79.4% correct level across 52 participants was 22.1 μs . One subject was not included in the average, because the fifth run was terminated after the adaptive variable exceeded 600 μs . This was surprising, because for the first four runs the subject had an average threshold ITD of 18.2 μs .

D. Discussion

The objective of experiment 2 was to determine accurate threshold ITDs for both trained and un-trained normal hearing listeners.

In this experiment, the condition from experiment 1 that yielded the smallest threshold ITD was selected for use in obtaining an accurate threshold ITD value for both trained and un-trained listeners. The chosen condition was the 20–1400 Hz band-pass filtered noise presented at 70 dB SPL with a short interstimulus interval of 50 ms which yielded the lowest threshold ITD of 10.0 μs at the 79.4% correct level in experiment 1. This condition was repetitively measured by the trained listeners in the shorter and more dedicated experiment 2, resulting in an average threshold ITD of 8.3 μs at 79.4% correct. However, to make a comparison to the historic data it is necessary to use 6.9 ($1 \pm 11.5\%$) μs which corresponds to 75% correct. This threshold is 23%, i.e., 2 standard errors below the lowest trustworthy reported threshold of 9 μs by Klumpp and Eady (1956). Note that Tobias and Zerlin (1959) report a 6 μs threshold for broadband noise. However, they presented the second interval either 6 μs left or 6 μs right leading, theoretically providing a 12 μs contrast between the possibilities.

To report this study's threshold ITDs we used geometric means to calculate the averages across subjects. This is meaningful when assuming a Gaussian distribution of log threshold ITD. Previously published data strongly hint at such a distribution (e.g., Yost *et al.*, 1974; Saberi, 1995), as does the present data from the 52 un-trained listeners (Fig. 7). In recent decades, geometric averaging has become a common practice. However, the studies from the 1950s (Klumpp and Eady, 1956; Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956) used arithmetic means. As they did not report any distribution or single subject data, we can only speculate that their distribution is similar to ours. In that case, the difference

between the two means is approximately 3%–4%, i.e., their geometric mean can be expected to be 0.3–0.4 μs lower than their reported arithmetic mean.

A larger effect is expected to be caused by the subject factor. The 1950s studies did not report if subjects underwent audiometric testing and whether they were clinically normal-hearing. Recent work has shown that factors such as age (Goupell *et al.*, 2017) and slight sub-clinical hearing loss (Bernstein and Trahiotis, 2016) critically influence binaural perception. In addition, subject related factors such as motivation, training, or fatigue cannot be easily quantified but can be expected to be important, as evidenced by the 1.6 μs lower thresholds compared to experiment 1. The selection of subjects and their training and motivation are seen as the critical factor, which limits the generality of the thresholds reported in experiment 2. We would not be surprised if a group of sound engineers or psychoacousticians yield even lower thresholds. That said, we have provided—to the best of our abilities—all the necessary background that will allow reproducibility of the results. Only when all these factors such as subject pool, training, and motivation are met do we expect average threshold ITDs within the above-given confidence interval of 6.9 ($1 \pm 11.5\%$) μs , or, simplified speaking, between 6 and 8 μs .

Threshold ITDs obtained from the un-trained listeners are also considerably lower than previously reported. Middlebrooks *et al.* (2013) reported an average threshold of 45 μs at the 79.4% correct level for a similar stimulus and method. Their subjects were, on average, 10 years older and deliberately not recruited from university students but rather from the general population. We speculate that the subject factor may be the main contributor to this factor of 2 difference. Our students included numerous audiology students and some psychology students, many of whom likely had prior exposure to psychophysics. We only excluded subjects with prior experience in dichotic listening experiments. As a result of the large relative variation of thresholds across un-trained subjects, the averaging technique (arithmetic in Middlebrooks *et al.* vs geometric here) contributes to the difference, but only marginally: in the current study the arithmetic mean is 2.3 μs higher than the above-stated geometric mean of 22.1 μs .

With all that said, it is still noteworthy that thresholds for un-trained listeners are 2.6 times higher than for trained listeners. We have investigated whether our relaxed inclusion criteria are part of the reason (inspired by Bernstein and Trahiotis, 2016). With only five subjects who had audiometric thresholds above 10 dB HL and the coarse audiometric testing, we cannot undertake a rigorous analysis regarding this issue. However, the average threshold ITD of those five subjects was 22.6 μs (79.4% correct level)—virtually identical to the grand mean, so there appears to be no strong effect.

IV. SUMMARY

The stimuli and methods used in this study yield results indicating that the lowest threshold ITDs in trained young normal-hearing listeners can be obtained with 20–1400 Hz band-pass filtered noise, in a two-interval L/R discrimination paradigm with a short interstimulus interval.

The average threshold ITD across nine trained listeners in a two-alternative forced choice task is $6.9 \mu\text{s}$ at the 75% correct level using the 20–1400 Hz band-pass filtered noise. The experimental accuracy of this value estimated from the 11.5% relative standard error of the mean is $0.8 \mu\text{s}$. Note that a $6.9 \mu\text{s}$ threshold ITD here means discriminating a target ITD of $+3.45 \mu\text{s}$ from a non-target ITD of $-3.45 \mu\text{s}$. Alternatively, for a $d' = 1$ (76% correct) an ITD of $7.2 \mu\text{s}$ is required and for the 79.4% correct level the ITD has to be $8.3 \mu\text{s}$. Two of the nine listeners performed significantly above chance at an ITD as small as $3.7 \mu\text{s}$. For 52 un-trained listeners, the average threshold ITD is $18.1 \mu\text{s}$ at the 75% correct level and $22.1 \mu\text{s}$ at the 79.4% correct level.

When reporting absolute threshold values from staircase procedures, reversal averages should be avoided as they are prone to strong bias. With reversal averaging, we would have erroneously stated a $7.3 \mu\text{s}$ threshold ITD from the three-down one-up method rather than the $8.3 \mu\text{s}$ at 79.4% correct.

The raw data, i.e., every button press, the experiment scripts, and the analysis scripts are freely available under a CC-BY 4.0 license in the supplementary material.¹ We hope this maximizes transparency of the experimental and analysis methods, and allows for easy reproducibility as well as for alternative data analysis techniques.

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¹See supplementary material at <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.5087566> for experiment and analysis scripts in MATLAB as well as raw data.

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